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A Look at the Karakalpak "Muxalles" Dutar Ensemble

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***Abstract:** This article discusses the establishment of the Muxalles Dutar Ensemble, which is affiliated with the Karakalpakstan Television and Radio Company. It covers information about both the current and previous members, as well as the repertoire.*

***Key words:** Baqsi, musician, namah, saz, Mu'alles, performing arts, repertoire, folk songs.*

The Karakalpak people have a rich historical heritage, with extensive development in literature, performing arts, including visual arts, architecture, theater, cinema, and especially music. In the cultural legacy of our ancestors, traditional songs and epic narratives related to significant events in the lives of the people have emerged, along with performers of traditional songs and music. These performers and their works have been preserved and passed down to us, leading to the early development of music culture.

In the first half of the 20th century, scholars began to study and analyze the repertoire of folk songs, traditional music, and epic poetry, highlighting their unique characteristics.

If we focus on this field, a performer who plays the dutar and sings is referred to as a baqsi in Karakalpak folk tradition. Through the repertoire performed by baqsi, we have inherited insights into the life of the Karakalpak people, their courage, loyalty to love, and dedication to their homeland.

The "Muxalles" dutar ensemble is one of the renowned folk ensembles, contributing significantly to preserving and passing down the traditional music of the Karakalpak people. The ensemble, named after the famous folk performer Genjebay Tilewmuratov, is part of the Union of Performing Arts under the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The ensemble was established in 1976 by the Karakalpak folk performer and State Prize laureate Berdaq, under the direction of the renowned master Genjebay Tilewmuratov. It was organized by the Karakalpakstan Television and Radio Company, initially consisting of 5 musicians and performers, including G. Tilewmuratov, G. Baylepesov, Q. Dosjanov, the singer K. Tinibaev, and O. Asanov. Over the years, the number of musicians and performers in the ensemble increased to 12-15-18.

After the passing of the master performer G. Tilewmuratov in 1997, in March 1998, the Uzbek folk performer G. O'temuratov was appointed as the artistic director of the ensemble. In February 2007, the ensemble was named in honor of the master performer G. Tilewmuratov.

The main objective of the ensemble is to preserve and transmit the forms of folk creativity of the Karakalpak people that have been shaped over generations and inherited from ancestors. Through traditional performances of Karakalpak national music, including epic poetry and song, the ensemble aims to foster deep respect and admiration for our priceless cultural heritage, especially among the younger generation, and to promote our national culture and values.

The ensemble actively participates in national celebrations and various republic-wide and international festivals, showcasing its repertoire and contributing to the promotion of our national culture.

Thanks to favorable conditions, the National Music Department was established at the Nukus School of Performing Arts in 1992. This department has attracted many young people interested in the arts, and the ensemble has been continuously enriched with new, talented young performers.

Members of the ensemble, including performers Z. Sharipova, the Karakalpak folk performer G. Allamberganova, N. Nuratdinov, and musician I. Saburova, have had the honor of presenting Karakalpak national music and performing arts in France, Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany, India, and South Korea.

In April 2007, the ensemble actively participated and emerged victorious at the International Theater and Folklore Festival held in Ashgabat, the capital of Turkmenistan. The ensemble has represented our people and national heritage in various countries, and continues to play a significant role in passing on our musical and cultural treasures to future generations. Today, the "Mu'alles" ensemble regularly participates in television and radio broadcasts with their performances.

In its ongoing activities, the ensemble has been a consistent participant in cultural days organized by the Republic of Bashkortostan, Dagestan, Tatarstan, Tashkent city, and the Khorezm region of Uzbekistan, contributing significantly to the promotion of our culture and arts.

Throughout its history, the ensemble has been distinguished by the following performers: G. Tilewmuratov, a 'Karakalpak Folk Performer' and 'State Prize Laureate named after Berdaq'; O. Asanov, G. Baylepesov, Q. Dosjanov, K. Tinibayev, T. Qurbanov, a 'Karakalpak Folk Artist'; G. Rametova, a 'Karakalpakstan Honored Artist'; A. Otarmaev, an 'Honored Figure in the Arts of Karakalpakstan' and 'Shukhrat Medal' recipient; I. Saburova, a 'Karakalpakstan Honored Cultural Worker'; G. Allamberganova, a 'Karakalpak Folk Performer'; Z. Sharipova, a recipient of the 'Uzbekistan Glory Medal' and 'Karakalpak Folk Performer'; L. Mukhammadinova, a 'Nihol' Prize laureate; U. Orinbaeva, a 'State Prize laureate named after Zulfiya'; as well as regional competition winners J. Qosimbetov, B. Palimbetova, B. Asqarova, J. Reymov, and G. Khamidov, who have all demonstrated their outstanding contributions.

The ensemble's repertoire includes national instruments and folk songs that have become classics, including: 'Ariwxan', 'Bozataw', 'Bes perde', 'Qara jorg'a', 'Ala qayis', 'Min' tu'men', 'Aqsingu'l', 'Jeti

asirim', 'Sanali keldi', 'Qoshim Palwan', 'Musa sen yari', 'Gu'baddin', 'Qiz minayim', 'Xosha da's', 'Ilme sultan', 'Nama basi', and others.

Since 2015, Jalgas Reymov has served as the artistic director of the 'Muxalles ensemble. Currently, the ensemble consists of 14 musicians and performers, who continue to contribute to the art.

Among the notable advancements in music culture over the years is the establishment of the Ajiniyaz State Pedagogical Institute in Nukus, named after Berdaq, and the State University of Karakalpakstan, as well as the creation of the State Institute of Performing Arts and Culture in Uzbekistan.

These institutions serve not only to enhance the availability of specialized education in our society but also to shape young people's perspectives on the arts and culture, thus contributing significantly to serving our people and fulfilling their responsibilities.

In accordance with the Presidential Decree PF-6000 of May 26, 2020, concerning the role and impact of 'Culture and Performing Arts in Society' and related initiatives, the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan has established the 'Department of Uzbek Maqam Performing Arts Faculty' at the Uzbekistan State Conservatory and the relevant educational programs at the State Institute of Performing Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan. This decree led to the founding of the Yunus Rajabiy Uzbek National Music Performing Arts Institute, which has begun its work. The institute focuses on training specialists in maqam performance, traditional singing, and major vocal studies, and it started its educational activities in the field of 'Folk Creativity (traditional singing and epic performance)' this year.

Although the institute has been established for a relatively short time, students have actively participated in the 'International Folk Singing Festival' held in our republic over the past 4 years, achieving award-winning positions. The students have also been successful in various international competitions, including those in France, Germany, and Finland, where they have presented their performing arts repertoires.

The purpose of providing information about the institute is to highlight that several of our esteemed teachers, who have contributed to the 'Muxalles' Dutar Ensemble, are also imparting the secrets of Karakalpak singing and playing to us. These include Injigu'l Saburova, an 'Honored Cultural Worker of the Republic of Karakalpakstan,' and Dinara Nuratdinova, a laureate of the 'Zulfiya' State Prize.

The 'Muxalles' Dutar Ensemble is renowned for its rich and diverse repertoire and its distinguished members, who are highly skilled and experienced. Due to the ensemble's esteemed reputation, not all performers can join; membership is a significant responsibility, requiring extensive knowledge of numerous instruments and songs. Initially, the ensemble was composed solely of the most eminent singers and musicians, and now it includes their most talented students. For this reason, the 'Muxalles' Dutar Ensemble, founded by G. Tilewmuratov, is considered highly significant in the realm of Karakalpak performance.

In summary, this ensemble is regarded as having a great historical legacy and considerable value. I am proud of the 'Muxalles' Dutar Ensemble for their continuous dedication and their role in presenting our national instruments and songs on the world stage. We have reason to take pride in the 'Muxalles, and I wish the ensemble members continued success in their artistry.

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